

Modelling and analysing cascading effects of cyberattacks to ATM systems

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Abstract - Digitalisation offers many benefits to Air Traffic Management (ATM), such as increased safety and airspace capacity, fewer delays and reduced fuel consumption. Yet, with technological innovations come challenges in managing new cyber security threats and risks. This paper presents an approach for modelling and analysing the effect of cascading effects of cyberattacks. The purpose is to allow security risk practitioners and system architects to better understand how cyber threats to their systems may impact other systems in the ATM ecosystem, and even in other sectors. The approach facilitates implementation of appropriate security measures and trust relationships in the ATM systems and underlying supply chains. The introduction of the Dependency Risk of Attack (DRoA) metric allows for a more nuanced assessment of risks, revealing that traditional risk management approaches may underestimate the true extent of vulnerabilities. The approach is demonstrated through an example in which cyber risk dependencies in three different systems are modelled and analysed, and we discuss some of the challenges that must be overcome in practice. The next steps include empirical validation through exercises with ATM stakeholders

Keywords – Air Traffic Management (ATM), cyber security, security risk assessment, security threats, cascading effects, supply chain security, SecRAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Air Traffic Management (ATM) is a complex global infrastructure that enables safe and efficient flow of air traffic. However, as the ATM systems become more interconnected and complex, the number and potential impact of cyber security risks towards these systems are increasing. According to the *Single European Sky ATM Research* (SESAR) Joint Undertaking [1], the progressive transition from traditional isolated legacy systems, which rely on domain specific protocols and applications, to modern, commercial-off-the-shelf IT systems, which use IP-based communication over shared public networks, will significantly change the operating environment, and thereby also the threat picture of the ATM landscape. This development is also expected to lead to longer and more complex supply chains in which stakeholders are becoming increasingly dependent on the services of other stakeholders, their industrial partners and related supply chains. The security of supply chains has been recognised by the *Aerospace Industries Association* (AIA) [2] as a great risk to aviation, since it allows multiple points for malicious actors to interfere with ATM organisations and their services. Further, the increased degree of interdependencies between ATM and other critical infrastructures increases its

complexity and thereby adds to the total risk [3].

To be able to provide safe and trustworthy services, organisations need to understand the cyber risk they are facing. More specifically, they need to understand how the components that their systems are constructed from are vulnerable, how the components of their systems interact with other components, and what would be the effect of security incidents targeting these components. Today, security risk assessment is the established approach to manage cyber risks. In the ATM community there are several established methods that are being followed, including the *Security Risk Assessment Methodology for SESAR* (SecRAM) [4].

However, a security risk assessment will always have a limited scope, meaning that it tends to focus on threats towards the stakeholder's own system components. A *cascading effect* is a phenomenon where a security threat propagates within a component, and/or to nearby components, either sequentially or concurrently, triggering one or more additional incidents, resulting in an overall consequence that is more severe than the consequence of the first security threat alone [5], [6]. Such cascading effects are of particular interest in interconnected and complex architectures and supply chains, where a security threat, which seemingly has an isolated and limited effect on a single IT system, may spread and lead to unexpected consequences to other systems and sectors than initially targeted. ATM organisations are no exception to such threats.

The potential impacts of cascading effects of attacks on services operated by linked infrastructures, or on services in the supply chains, are often overlooked in risk assessments of ATM systems. For instance, in 2022, a Boeing-owned subsidiary, Jeppesen, confirmed that a cyber incident had impacted flight planning and communication software, causing flight delays for airlines using their services [7]. In 2023 [8], cascading effects caused more than 4000 flights to be delayed and 600 cancelled in the US because of an outage in the *Notice to Airmen* (NOTAM) system, which provides essential information to pilots. Even more recently, in July 2024, there was a Microsoft Azure outage that affected aviation services worldwide [9] due to a faulty third party software update from the CrowdStrike security firm. As reported in [10], “So it wasn’t just computers that were affected, but servers and a host of other systems as well. Overwhelming requests from users, devices, services and businesses ushered in a cascading series of failures with Microsoft products – namely Azure Cloud and Microsoft 365”. These incidents show that there is an urgent need to

better understand more complex risks in ATM systems.

This paper addresses the research question: *How to model and analyse cascading effects of cyberattacks to ATM systems?* It is organised as follows. In Section II, we provide an overview of related work. In Section III, we explain the basic definitions from SecRAM [4], which we have used in our approach. Section IV then presents our approach. In Section V, we provide an example of its use, and section VI discusses related challenges and future work. Section VII concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Several studies have explored cascading effects in cyber-physical systems, particularly within critical infrastructures. For instance, Schauer et al. [11] presented a formal model to describe the propagation of threats through various physical and cyber assets within critical infrastructures, demonstrating the cascading effects using a maritime port infrastructure. Similarly, Palleti et al. [12] investigated the cascading effects of cyber-attacks on interdependent critical infrastructures, such as a water treatment plant and a water distribution system. Papadopoulos et al. [13] have created a framework for detecting both cyber and physical threats and create alerts on cascading effects. These studies emphasize the importance of understanding interdependencies and the potential for wide-reaching impacts across interconnected systems. He et al. [5] have analysed security threats posed by cascading failure in cyber-physical systems and included a comprehensive survey on methods for failure modelling and vulnerability analysis. Their results show that when humans and widely interconnected components are involved, the increased uncertainty can cause cascading failures to propagate beyond expectations. They also argue that the body of research is insufficient for the development of a systematic protection framework. One of the most systematic approaches is an analysis of common cause failures in critical infrastructures described by Kotzanikolaou et al. in [14] and [15]. Their approach can be applied to the aviation domain assuming the following equivalences:

- Critical infrastructure \Leftrightarrow Supporting asset
- Common cause failure \Leftrightarrow Successful cyberattack

To the best of our knowledge, only a few studies have considered the aviation domain, and then mostly in very specific technical domains (e.g., ADS-B spoofing) [6] or environments (e.g., the airport [16]). Piekert et al. [17] discuss how malicious activities at critical infrastructures linked to airports can cause knock-on effects throughout the air transport network. They conclude that there are many unanswered questions, such that lack of information about ongoing attacks limits early awareness and mitigation efforts on operations.

III. BACKGROUND: BASIC DEFINITIONS ADOPTED FROM SecRAM

To understand and model the impacts of the cascading effects of an attack, we have adopted some of the definitions from SecRAM. First, according to SecRAM, *Primary Assets* (PAs) are the intangible functions, services, processes or information that are part of the ATM system, and that have value to the system. A successful attack impairing a PA will therefore cause harm to the ATM system, by affecting its performance, capacity, safety, etc. *Supporting Assets* (SAs)

are the entities which enable the PAs. Examples are hardware, software, network connections and people. The SAs may possess vulnerabilities that are exploitable by threats aiming to impair the PAs. From the cascading effect point of view, we are hence interested in understanding and modelling how the SAs in an ATM system are connected to each other (and to SAs in other systems, infrastructures, and sectors), how cyberattacks can propagate from one SA to another, and what would be the attack consequences for the PAs that all the connected SAs are enabling.

Second, according to SecRAM, a cyber security risk is defined as "*the potential that a given threat will exploit vulnerabilities of an asset or group of assets and thereby have an impact on the identified assets*". We have adopted this basic understanding of risk, but, for the purpose of this paper, we have further formalised it as:

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Vulnerability to the attack} * \text{Impact} \quad (1)$$

where "Vulnerability to the attack" and "Impact" are both numbers in [0,1]. We are using "Vulnerability to the attack" instead of "Attack probability/likelihood", and this allows us to analyse worst-case scenarios, meaning that we assume that all attacks will have the same probability of becoming manifested. It is therefore the SA's vulnerability to the attack, together with the "Impact" of the attack, that is relevant for assessing the risk.

Third, SecRAM defines impact as "the extent to which a loss of confidentiality, availability or integrity of an asset affects the achievement of business objectives". In SecRAM, the impact value is assessed for seven different areas: people, capacity, performance, economic, branding, regulatory and environment, and it is assessed according to security attributes confidentiality, integrity and availability. In SecRAM the impact values range from 1 to 5 according to pre-defined scales. When applying SecRAM, a table like the one in Table 1 will therefore be generated for each PA (after conversion into [0,1] values).

TABLE 1. ASSESSING IMPACT VALUES OF AN ATTACK IN SecRAM

Primary Asset	Security attribute	People	Capacity	Performance	Economic	Branding	Regulatory	Environment	Maximum impact
PA#1	C	3	1	1	1	1	3	1	3
	I	5	4	1	2	3	1	1	5
	A	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	4

In this example, we see that the maximum impact value, which represents the worst-case scenario of the attack, is 5. This value represents the potential consequence on *people*, if there is a *breach of integrity* of the primary asset PA#1. Note that in SecRAM, the definition of impact value 5 on people is "Fatalities", meaning that people may die if this worst-case scenario would manifest itself. In the risk assessment, this impact value will then be inherited by all the SAs that enable the PA and used when computing the risk of attacks on these SAs.

Fig. 1. Example of cascading effects

IV. IMPACTS OF CASCADING EFFECTS

Our proposed approach consists of the following steps:

- 1) Identify the PAs and SAs in the ATM system.
- 2) Identify and model the dependencies between the SAs, within the system and across system boundaries.
- 3) Model the impact of the cascading effects on the SAs and, consequently, on the PAs that are supported by the SAs.
- 4) Compute the dependency risks of the attacks (DRoA) towards the SAs in the ATM system.
- 5) Assess the risk on each PA as a cumulative impact of the SAs supporting it.
- 6) Assess the related costs.

The first step on identifying PAs and SAs is "standard procedure" in most security risk assessment methodologies, including SecRAM, and will therefore not be described here. Steps 2-6 are detailed in the following subsections.

A. Identifying and modelling dependencies

To understand how cascading effects of attacks may spread in a complex system, we need to identify and model dependencies between the components (i.e., the SAs). In the ATM domain, the following dependencies are relevant to consider:

- **Physical dependency:** In this case, the state of a SA depends upon the material output(s) of another SA (e.g., an aircraft tank physically depends on a refuelling device).
- **Cyber dependency:** The state of a SA depends on information produced and transmitted through another SA (e.g. a flight management software depends on a server).
- **Geographic dependency:** The state of a SA is impacted by another SA since they are co-located (e.g., all aircraft landing at airport A are geographically dependent on the control tower of airport A).
- **Logical dependency:** In this case, the state of a SA depends upon the state of another SA via a non-physical, non-cyber, or non-geographic connection (e.g., the punctuality reputation of an airline logically depends on the punctuality of its aircraft).
- **Human dependency:** SAs are handled by the same humans (e.g. both radio communication and signal light guns are operated by an ATCO).

Based on these types of dependencies, we can observe 1) the propagation of cyberattacks from one SA to another SA is only possible if the two SAs are cyber-dependent, and/or 2) the effects of a cyberattack on one SA can cascade to other SAs (and then impact their supported PAs) through any of these dependencies.

Inspired by the cyberattack to Jeppesen in 2022 [7] (see Section I), the effect of a shutdown of a ground access router due to a cyberattack may also cascade to

- 1) the air-ground (A/G) communication service (cyber dependency),
- 2) the landing aircraft (logical dependency on A/G communication), and
- 3) the passengers on the landing aircraft (geographical dependency on the aircraft).

B. Modelling impact of cascading effects

Our approach to assess the impact of the cascading effects on the SAs and, consequently, on the PAs that are supported by the SAs, is visualised in Fig. 1. Here, there are three Primary Assets (PA₁, PA₂, and PA₃) and several SAs enabling one or more of these PAs (e.g., SA₃ is enabling both PA₁ and PA₂). In this example, the impact I on PA₁ is potentially generated by the impacts generated on SA₁, SA₂ and SA₃, formally expressed as:

$$I(\text{PA}_1) = I(\text{SA}_1 \rightarrow \text{PA}_1) + I(\text{SA}_2 \rightarrow \text{PA}_1) + I(\text{SA}_3 \rightarrow \text{PA}_1) \quad (2)$$

There are two possible types of cascading effects:

- **Cyberattack propagation**, i.e., an attack that exploits a SA to attack other SAs. For example, referring to Fig. 1, a possible cascading effect due to cyberattack propagation is the following:
 - SA₁ is the victim of a successful cyberattack.
 - The successful cyberattack to SA₁ propagates, e.g., to connected Supporting Assets SA₄ and then further to SA₅.
 - This implies that PA₁, PA₂, and PA₃ may all be impacted by a successful cyberattack to SA₁ that propagates to the other SAs.
- **Impact propagation**, i.e., the cyberattack to an SA does not propagate to other SAs, e.g. a distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attack, but the reduced performance of the victim SA will impact other SAs. For example, referring again to Fig. 1, a possible cascading effect due to post-attack impact propagation is the following:
 - SA₁ is the victim of a successful cyberattack.

- The attack changes the state of SA₄ (e.g. 50% performance reduction), because it is logically dependent on SA₁.
- The change of state of SA₄ then has an impact on the connected assets SA₃ and SA₅, since they both depend on SA₄ (e.g., the 50% performance reduction of SA₄ will worsen the performance of both SA₃ and SA₅ by 25% each).
- This implies that PA₁, PA₂ and PA₃ will be impacted by a successful cyberattack to SA₁, even though the attack itself did not propagate to any of the other SAs.

The two effects above can be combined into a chain of events.

C. Compute the dependency risks

To understand the risk of a cascading effect, we introduce the notion **Dependency Risk of Attack** (DRoA) for the dependency SA_i → SA_j, which is defined as:

$$DRoA_{ij} = V_{ij} \cdot I_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where V_{ij} represents a vulnerability where an attack can propagate from SA_i to SA_j, and I_{ij} is the qualitative impact value that will suffer SA_j if SA_i is victim of a successful attack. Both can take values in the range [0,1]. To simplify the estimations of impact and vulnerability, it is possible to use one of the qualitative values {VL, L, M, H, VH}, from *Very Low* to *Very High*, by applying a discretisation as follows: VL = [0–0.05), L = [0.05–0.25), M = [0.25–0.5), H = [0.5–0.75) and VH = [0.75–1]). Following the qualitative approach, DRoA_{ij} can then be calculated and visualised using a risk matrix, like the one exemplified in Table 2.

TABLE 2 AN EXAMPLE OF A RISK MATRIX TO VISUALISE DRoA_{ij}

DRoA _{ij}		V _{ij}				
		VL	L	M	H	VH
I _{ij}	VL	VL	L	L	M	M
	L	L	L	M	M	H
	M	L	M	M	H	H
	H	M	M	H	H	VH
	VH	M	H	H	VH	VH

It is important to note that:

- Vulnerability V_{ij} is strictly linked to the choice of the attack types and therefore calculations shall be done for each type of attack.
- Impact I_{ij} should be linked to the seven SecRAM types of impacts: people, capacity, performance, economic, branding, regulatory and environment.
- V_{ij} strongly depends on dependency type $i \rightarrow j$ (i.e., it can propagate only in case of cyber-dependencies).
- I_{ij} strongly depends on attack type and the affected assets.

As previously shown by Kotzanikolaou et al. [14], the vulnerability V_{1M} of the Supporting Asset SA_M at the end of the chain SA₁ ... SA_M becomes:

$$V_{1,M} = \prod_{i=1}^{M-1} V_{i,i+1} \quad (4)$$

The heuristic justification of this equation stems from the analogy between conditional degrees of belief and conditional probabilities. Since each $V_{i,i+1}$ is a conditional degree of belief, then the joint event is simply the product of all the conditional degrees of belief. The risk DRoA_{1M} then becomes:

$$DRoA_{1,M} = \sum_{i=1}^M DRoA_{i,i+1} = \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\prod_{j=1}^i V_{j,j+1} \right) \cdot I_{i,i+1} \quad (5)$$

D. Assess the risk on each PA

Having defined the dependencies and the DRoA, it is necessary to understand how to assess the risk on each PA. Through the analysis of the dependencies, it is then possible to propagate the risk to the PAs supported by the considered SAs and analyse related impacts using standard risk assessment techniques. The example in the next section will illustrate how these steps can be applied for an existing ATM system.

E. Defining the related costs

As soon as the risk on each PA is assessed, it is necessary to define:

- The value associated to the direct and indirect consequences on the organisation's PAs and SAs (or, in other words, the intangible and tangible assets).
- The attack-related costs associated to the simple fact of being a victim of a successful cyberattack.

Since the definition of asset-related costs has already been widely researched and reported in scientific and technical literature (e.g., [18], [19], and [20]), we consider this step to be out of scope of this paper.

V. EXAMPLE: CASCADING EFFECTS OF AN ATTACK AGAINST CPDLC IN THE CONTEXT OF THE FUTURE COMMUNICATION INFRASTRUCTURE

To demonstrate how to apply the methodology, we consider the simplified example model in Fig. 2. Here, three seemingly independent systems are visualised:

- 1) In the first system (green box), IP connectivity (i.e., the PA) is provided as a service in the Future Communications Infrastructure (FCI). In this example, we consider three SAs that enable the PA; a ground-to-ground (G/G) router, an air-to-ground (A/G) router and an LDACS datalink (LDACS is an upcoming air-to-ground communications standard and stands for L-band Digital Aeronautical Communications System); all of them are connected with each other to allow seamless data transmission between the air- and ground-based ATM systems.
- 2) In the second system (purple box), the PA CPDLC service (enables communication between the pilot and air traffic controller and stands for Controller Pilot Data Link Communications) is provided as a service over multilink through two independent datalinks: LDACS and SATCOM (short for satellite communications datalink), which are the SAs in this system. Notably, the LDACS datalink is the same SA as the one utilised in the first system
- 3) In the third system (yellow box), we consider a

Fig. 2 Example of an application of the proposed cascading effects methodology

maritime system that provides a Long-Range Identification and Tracking (LRIT) service [21] (i.e., the PA) relying on a SATCOM datalink (SA), which is provided by the same service provider as in the second ATM system.

A. Risks propagation

In a normal case, the security risks in these three systems would be assessed independently of each other. However, as seen in Fig. 2, there are obvious dependencies between the different components (SAs) used in the different systems, which implies there can be cascading effects of cyberattacks towards any of the SAs in any of these three systems: across systems, or even across sectors.

It is now possible to imagine the following cyberattack scenario: a Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attack is successfully hitting the G/G router in the FCI, then it propagates to the A/G router, and, in this way, it shuts down or severely slows down the LDACS datalink. The dependencies between these three SAs are therefore cyber dependencies. There will also be a logical dependency between LDACS and SATCOM, because a performance reduction in one of these services may overload the other service, because of the multilink feature in the FCI. Table 3 depicts an overview of these dependencies.

TABLE 3 DEPENDENCY TYPES

Link	Dependency
DDoS → G/G router	Cyber
G/G router → A/G router	Cyber
G/G router → LDACS	Cyber
LDACS → SATCOM	Logic

To further illustrate the example, we define the following vulnerability and impact values (Table 4) for the involved SAs using the implied probability ranges previously defined.

For the sake of simplification, we have made the hypothesis that it is relatively unlikely that a DDoS attack will be successfully executed in the FCI, but if successful, then the vulnerability of the dependent assets becomes greater.

TABLE 4. VULNERABILITY AND IMPACT VALUES

SAs	Vulnerability		Impact	
DDoS → G/G router	0.04	VL	0.6	H
G/G router → A/G router	0.70	H	0.9	VH
G/G router → LDACS	0.9	VH	0.9	VH

In a standard SecRAM risk assessment of the first ATM system, which provides IP connectivity, only the effect of the DDoS attack towards the G/G router would have been considered, concluding that the risk level of this attack is:

$$R = 0.04 \cdot 0.6 = 0.024 \quad (6)$$

which is a *very low* (VL) risk.

However, if all the cascading effects are considered, the DRoA becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} DRoA &= \\ &0.04 \cdot 0.6 + 0.04 \cdot 0.7 \cdot 0.9 + 0.04 \cdot 0.7 \cdot 0.9 \cdot 0.9 \\ &= 0.07 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

i.e., a *low* (L) risk, which clearly is higher than the risk value assessed with the current SecRAM approach.

B. Impacts propagation

Here, we analyse the cascading impacts on the PAs in the same example. Again, if a standard SecRAM risk assessment had been applied, the only impact considered would have been the effect of the reduced performances on the FCI IP connectivity due to the reduced availability of the G/G router. However, a more detailed analysis of the cascading impacts on PAs supported by the involved SAs will show that:

- The attack to the G/G router can impact the FCI IP connectivity.
- The propagation to the A/G router can worsen the FCI IP connectivity, and, as further impact, may shut down the LDACS datalink.
- The lack of the LDACS will force to switch to SATCOM datalink.
- Switching to SATCOM will imply a flooding of messages on this channel and therefore a potential CPDLC service degradation.

- Moreover, the SATCOM bandwidth within a cell is normally shared between different customers and, in particular, with maritime services.
- Therefore, the analysed cascading effects may also lead to reducing the performances of the maritime LRIT service.

To show the huge implications of this cyberattack, we concentrate now on the CPDLC degradation. The main consequences of a successful attack that degrades the CPDLC service are that

- it will be necessary to temporarily revert from CPDLC to voice [26], and, therefore,
- more separation may be needed (e.g., in the North Atlantic Region [27] or in the Reykjavik CTA [28]).

The cascading effects of the above consequences in terms of impact are represented in the diagram in Fig. 3. They are described according to the type of impact categories listed in SecRAM [4] and according to the possible involved stakeholders:

- ANSP - Air Navigation Service Providers (in green),
- Airlines (in violet),
- Airports (in yellow), and
- Passengers (in orange).

It is worth noting that:

- This type of cyber-attack will not influence people's safety.
- All other SecRAM impact categories are involved and their costs may be extremely high.
- Cascading effects are significant and involve several stakeholders whose interest are sometime contrasting. It is therefore extremely important to carry out risk assessment approaches widening their scope to the entire supply chain.
- The ANSPs' liability aspects (penalties and increased insurance premiums) are difficult to assess due to the specific status of ANSPs in different EU countries (e.g., nationally controlled, fully private, etc.) and the confidentiality of the matter.
- The increased insurance premiums due to poor execution of tasks as victim of a cyber-attack are regulated by point ATM/ANS.OR.D.020 of EU Reg. 2017/373 [29].

Clearly, this is a more complex scenario than the one offered by a traditional risk management approach such as SecRAM, and this allows to assess in much more detail the possible impacts of cyberattacks to ATM assets.

VI. DISCUSSION AND FURTHER WORK

The study of cascading effects in cyber-physical systems has been extensive, yet its application to the aviation domain remains limited. This paper extends the analysis of common cause failures in critical infrastructures to the aviation sector. We highlight the critical need for a comprehensive understanding of dependencies within the ATM system to effectively model and mitigate cascading effects of

cyberattacks. While previous research has primarily addressed physical and cyber interdependencies, our work extends this analysis to include logical, geographic and human dependencies, providing a more comprehensive view of potential cascading effects in aviation.

The adoption of SecRAM definitions and methodology provides a structured approach to assess and manage risks, providing a valuable contribution to our guiding research question; *how to model and analyse cascading effects of cyberattacks to ATM systems?* However, we have identified quite a few challenges that still needs to be overcome during practical assessments:

- **Wicked problems** are complex issues that are difficult to define and have no clear solution [22]. In the context of aviation and cyber risk management, these problems often involve multiple stakeholders with conflicting interests, evolving threats, and uncertain outcomes.

Addressing risks caused by wicked problems requires adaptive and iterative approaches, stakeholder collaboration, and the ability to manage uncertainty and ambiguity. Solutions to wicked problems are often provisional and require ongoing adjustment and refinement.

- **Node explosion** refers to the rapid increase in the number of SAs (nodes) in a system as dependencies are mapped out [23]. In the aviation context, this can lead to highly complex models that are difficult to manage and analyse.

The sheer volume of nodes can overwhelm computational resources and make it challenging to identify critical paths and vulnerabilities. Simplifying these models without losing essential details is a significant challenge.

- Defining the **scope and boundaries** of the system under analysis is crucial but challenging [24]. In aviation, systems are interconnected with numerous other systems, both within and outside the aviation domain.

Determining where to draw the line for analysis can be subjective and may lead to either an overly narrow focus that misses critical dependencies or an overly broad scope that becomes unmanageable. Balancing comprehensiveness with practicality is essential.

- **Unknown/hidden dependencies** are those that are not immediately apparent or documented. These can arise from complex interactions between systems, human factors, or third-party services.

Identifying these hidden dependencies requires thorough investigation and often relies on expert knowledge and historical data. Failure to uncover these dependencies can lead to incomplete risk assessments and unexpected cascading effects.

- **Outdated or incorrect dependency information** can lead to flawed risk assessments and mitigation strategies. Dependencies within aviation systems will change over time due to updates, upgrades, or changes in operational procedures. Keeping dependency data current and accurate is a continuous

challenge, requiring regular audits and updates to the system models.

- **Overestimating risks** can lead to overly conservative decisions, create a culture of fear and misallocation of resources. The focus on worst-case scenarios in SecRAM may lead to such an overestimation of risks, necessitating a balanced approach in practical applications.

On the contrary, **underestimation of risks**, e.g., caused by optimistic bias, can have fatal

consequences as seen with the Boeing 737 MAX Program [25].

While our methodology offers a systematic approach, it is primarily theoretical and requires empirical validation. Future research will aim to empirically validate the proposed approach through exercises with key aviation stakeholders. Additionally, expanding the scope to include more diverse types of ATM systems and dependencies, various attack scenarios and tool support will enhance the robustness of the approach. By addressing these areas, the aviation sector can better prepare for and mitigate the cascading effects of

Fig. 3 Diagram of cascading impacts in case of CPDLC degradation

cyberattacks, ensuring greater resilience and safety in air traffic management systems.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper has extended the analysis of cascading effects in cyber-physical systems to the aviation domain, highlighting the critical need for a comprehensive understanding of dependencies within *Air Traffic Management* (ATM) systems, but also towards the surrounding environment. Based on the SecRAM definitions and methodology, we have provided a structured approach to assess and manage the risks associated with cyberattacks and their cascading effects.

Our findings underscore the importance of considering both cyberattack propagation and impact propagation when evaluating the potential consequences of cyber threats. The introduction of the *Dependency Risk of Attack* (DRoA) metric allows for a more nuanced assessment of risks, revealing that traditional risk management approaches may underestimate the true extent of vulnerabilities.

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